

Heterocyclic Compounds: Reaction of Indoles with Dienophiles

J. R. Merchant and S. S. Salgar

In a previous communication¹, the reaction of indoles with dienophiles, like β -nitrostyrenes, forming addition compounds was reported. The present work describes the condensation of different indoles with methyl vinyl ketone (I) under the experimental conditions, recorded in Table I.

Previous work on the subject was carried out by only Szmuskovicz² who employed acetic acid or acetic anhydride for the condensation. In the present work, indole and 2-methyl- and 2-phenylindoles have been allowed to react with (I) to yield adducts of the general structure:

[Ia: R=H. Ib: R=Me. Ic: R=Ph]

Generally equimolecular quantities of the reactants were used and the progress of the reaction was indicated by darkening of the mixture, finally yielding colorless adducts, which were characterised by preparation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. It appears that the best yields of the adducts are obtained in presence of a mixture of acetic acid and acetic anhydride. As reported by Szmuskovicz², 2-methylindole also gives 2-methylcarbazole, if heated with (I) at 280° in presence of a small amount of hydroquinone.

TABLE I

No.	Conditions.	Temp.	Time.	%Yields of adducts obtained with			
				Indole.	2-Me-indole.	2-Ph-indole.	3-Me-indole.
1.	With water containing SO ₂ in presence of hydroquinone	60°	1½ hr.	33	Nil	Nil	Nil
2.	In absence of solvent	155-62°	5-6	20	28	Nil	Nil
3.	With acetic acid only	100°	½ to ½	65	68	54	Nil
4.	With acetic acid in presence of acetic anhydride	100°	½	72	80	60	8 (heat for 2-3 hrs.)
5.	With hydroquinone only	280-90°	30	Nil	9	Nil	Nil

1. Salgar and Merchant, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1961, 14, 108.

2. Szmuskovicz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 79, 2818.

As expected, 3-methylindole does not form an adduct under the usual experimental conditions. In presence of acetic acid-acetic anhydride, it affords, however, the adduct as an oil in very poor yields*.

1-(3'-Indolyl)-butan-3-one (IIa).—Sulphur dioxide was passed in water (2.5 ml) for about 10 minutes and indole (1.5 g.) and hydroquinone (25 mg.) were added; the mixture was shaken and heated on a water bath at about 60°. Methyl vinyl ketone (about 2 g. of 85% solution) was added in small amounts with frequent shaking. A yellow solid mass separated after about 20-30 minutes. The reaction mixture was further heated for an hour with stirring and then chilled. The yellow solid after crystallisation from dilute ethanol gave colorless needles, m.p. 92-93°, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 7.0. C₁₂H₁₃ON requires C, 76.97; H, 7.0%).

The 2,4-DNP crystallised from acetic acid in dark orange crystals, m.p. 207-208°. (Found: N, 19.0. C₁₈H₁₇O₄N₃ requires N, 19.06%).

The oxime crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°), m.p. 89°. (Found: N, 14.1. C₁₂H₁₄ON₂ requires N, 13.85%).

1-[3'-(2'-Methyl)-indolyl]-butan-3-one (IIb) was prepared according to the method described by Szmuszkowicz². The adduct was obtained as an oil, b.p. 180-90°/0.05 mm, the 2,4-DNP of which crystallised from acetic acid in red crystals, m.p. 210-12°. (Found: N, 18.6. C₁₆H₁₉O₄N₃ requires N, 18.38%).

1-[3'-(2'-Phenyl)-indolyl]-butan-3-one (IIc).—To a solution of 2-phenylindole (480 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (12 ml) were added acetic anhydride (4 ml) and methyl vinyl ketone (540 mg.). The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 minutes and then heated on a water bath for 45 minutes. The dark brown liquid was cooled and the crystals separating after adding water (100ml) were filtered and washed with ~~water~~. Recrystallisation from dilute ethanol and sublimation under vacuum gave colorless needles, m.p. 112-13°, yield 60.4%. (Found: C, 82.3; H, 6.5. C₁₈H₁₇ON requires C, 82.13; H, 6.46%).

Its 2,4-DNP after crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave red crystals, m.p. 232°. (Found: N, 16.3. C₂₄H₂₁O₄N₃ requires N, 15.85%).

1-[2'-(3'-Methyl)indolyl]-butan-3-one was prepared according to the method described by Szmuszkowicz². The adduct was obtained as an oil, b.p. 170-90°/0.05 mm. Its 2,4,-DNP crystallised from ethanol in red prisms, m.p. 95-97°.